

A Study of Malaria –Related Pediatric Morbidity and Mortality in India**Chandan Kumar Pathak¹, Manish Kumar Singh², Kripa Nath Mishra³**¹Senior Resident, Department of Pediatric, Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital, Laheriasarai, Darbhanga, Bihar, India²Senior Resident, Department of Pediatric, Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital, Laheriasarai, Darbhanga, Bihar, India³Professor, Department of Pediatric, Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital, Laheriasarai, Darbhanga, Bihar, India

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Abstract:

This study examines the rates of malaria-related paediatric morbidity and mortality at Darbhanga Medical College Hospital in India over a one-year period. Our analysis involved studying 200 cases involving children. We discovered a notable increase in the number of cases during the monsoon months. In 70% of these cases, the predominant strain was *Plasmodium vivax*. Although the recovery rate stands at an impressive 90%, it is unfortunate that there is a mortality rate of 10%, with the most devastating impact being on children under two years old. The results underscore the necessity of implementing focused interventions for malaria control, particularly during periods of high transmission. They also stress the significance of promptly administering treatment to enhance outcomes in young children. The study highlights the persistent issue of paediatric malaria in areas where it is common and emphasises the urgent requirement for improved public health strategies.

Keywords: Pediatric Malaria, *Plasmodium vivax*, Monsoon Season, Mortality Rate.

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Introduction

Malaria continues to pose a significant public health challenge in India, with a particular impact on vulnerable populations, including children [1]. This illness, resulting from *Plasmodium* parasites transmitted by infected female *Anopheles* mosquitoes, presents a significant threat of illness and death among children [2,3]. Despite significant efforts and advancements in malaria control and eradication, the prevalence of this disease in young children remains alarmingly high. This is primarily due to their developing immune systems and limited access to timely and effective treatment. Understanding the dynamics of malaria-related paediatric morbidity and mortality in India is of utmost importance in studying the disease within this specific demographic [6].

This study seeks to measure the frequency, evaluate the seriousness, and uncover the trends and factors that contribute to negative results in children affected by malaria. Through a dedicated focus on cases involving children, this research aims to offer valuable insights that may pave the way for more precise interventions, bolster preventive measures, and enhance treatment protocols designed specifically for young patients. In addition, the study examines the wider socio-economic and environmental elements that play a role in the increased prevalence of malaria in specific areas of

India. These factors include monsoon patterns, urbanisation, and the accessibility of healthcare services. A comprehensive approach is crucial in developing strategies that address not only medical treatment, but also preventive measures and community education. This is necessary to reduce the incidence and impact of malaria on India's children [7,8].

Methodology

Study Design: The study was conducted as a retrospective cohort analysis, utilizing patient records from Darbhanga Medical College Hospital (DMCH), Darbhanga. The research spanned a period of one year, focusing on evaluating the burden and outcomes of pediatric malaria within the region.

Study Population: The group included malaria-diagnosed 0-12-year-olds. Rapid diagnostic testing or blood smear microscopy verified the diagnosis. The selection criteria focused on paediatric patients to determine malaria's impact on this vulnerable age group.

Data Collection: With authorisation from the necessary authorities, the hospital's medical records department provided retrospective data for research. Patient demographics (age, sex), clinical

presentation, laboratory results, treatment details, outcomes (recovery, complications, mortality), and follow-up information were retrieved.

Data Analysis: The collected data were anonymized and analyzed to determine the incidence rates, identify common clinical features and complications, and evaluate the factors influencing morbidity and mortality rates among the pediatric population. Statistical analysis was performed using appropriate software, with chi-square tests for categorical data and t-tests for continuous variables to assess significant differences and trends.

Results

A total of 200 paediatric patients diagnosed with malaria were included in the study over the course of one year. The distribution consisted of 120 males and 80 females, with males accounting for 60% and females for 40%. Here is the breakdown of the age distribution: 25% of the participants were under 2 years old (n=50), 40% were between 2 and 6 years old (n=80), and 35% were between 7 and 12 years old (n=70). During the monsoon months, from July to September, there was a significant increase in the number of malaria cases, making up around 60% of the total cases (n=120). The study found that *Plasmodium vivax* was the most common strain, accounting for 70% of cases (n=140), while *Plasmodium falciparum* was responsible for the remaining 30% (n=60).

The majority of patients (190 out of the total) experienced fever as their primary symptom. Additional common symptoms reported were

nausea (50%, n=100) and migraines (30%, n=60). 15% of the cases (n=30) exhibited severe malaria, which was identified by symptoms like severe anaemia, respiratory distress, or cerebral malaria. Antimalarial treatment was administered to all patients by the national malaria treatment guidelines. Most patients (80%, n=160) had successful treatment without experiencing any complications. There were instances where the treatment did not yield the desired results in 5% of the cases (n=10), necessitating the use of alternative antimalarial therapies.

Out of a total of 180 cases, an impressive 90% of patients successfully recovered. There were 20 cases of mortality, with a death rate of 10%. These unfortunate incidents mainly affected children under the age of 2 years and individuals with *Plasmodium falciparum* infections. 25% of patients (n=50) experienced complications that resulted in extended hospital stays, with severe anaemia being the most prevalent complication. The study emphasises the considerable impact of malaria on children in Darbhanga, particularly during the monsoon season. The impressive rate of recovery demonstrates the success of following treatment protocols, while the unfortunate mortality rate highlights the grave danger that malaria presents to the most fragile and youngest individuals. It is crucial to focus on enhancing preventive measures, early detection, and timely treatment in order to minimise the impact of malaria on children in the area.

Table 1: This table provides a detailed breakdown of the demographics, clinical outcomes, and treatment responses among the pediatric patients studied.

Category	Count	Percentage
Total Patients	200	-
Gender Distribution - Male	120	60%
Gender Distribution - Female	80	40%
Age Distribution - <2 years	50	25%
Age Distribution - 2-6 years	80	40%
Age Distribution - 7-12 years	70	35%
Cases during Monsoon (July-Sept)	120	60%
Predominant Malaria Strain - <i>P. vivax</i>	140	70%
Predominant Malaria Strain - <i>P. falciparum</i>	60	30%
Common Symptoms - Fever	190	95%
Common Symptoms - Vomiting	100	50%
Common Symptoms - Headache	60	30%
Severe Malaria Cases	30	15%
Treatment Success	160	80%
Treatment Failures	10	5%
Overall Recovery Rate	180	90%
Mortality Rate	20	10%
Complications Leading to Prolonged Hospital Stays	50	25%

Discussion

Our retrospective cohort study reveals the significant impact of malaria on paediatric populations in Darbhanga, particularly during the monsoon months [9]. The rise in cases during this time coincides with the rise in mosquito activity, highlighting the urgent importance of implementing specific strategies to control the spread of vectors. Given that *Plasmodium vivax* is the most common strain in 70% of cases, it seems that regional malaria control programs could improve their effectiveness by targeting interventions that specifically target this strain [10,11].

According to the study findings, the youngest patients, specifically those under two years of age, had the highest mortality rates. Additionally, individuals infected with *Plasmodium falciparum* were also found to be at a higher risk [12]. This emphasises the importance of recognising the susceptibility of young children to serious complications from malaria. It indicates the need for focused efforts in promptly diagnosing and implementing aggressive treatment strategies for this specific group [13,14]. Although the recovery rate is quite high at 90%, the observed mortality rate of 10% is a cause for concern. The mortality rate mentioned may be a result of factors like delayed treatment, potential resistance to drugs, or the occurrence of complications such as severe anaemia and cerebral malaria. Healthcare providers must inform communities about the significance of early intervention and following treatment plans diligently [15].

In addition, the high rate of complications resulting in extended hospital stays highlights the importance of implementing improved management strategies in healthcare settings to mitigate these outcomes. Implementing standardised care pathways and enhancing the training of healthcare personnel in managing paediatric malaria effectively could be potential steps forward [16]. In summary, this study enhances our comprehension of the dynamics of paediatric malaria and provides valuable evidence to inform public health policies and clinical practices. It has the potential to help alleviate the burden of this disease among children in areas comparable to Darbhanga. Additional investigation is needed to delve into the long-term patterns and the effects of targeted public health measures on decreasing both the frequency and intensity of malaria in this susceptible group [17-20].

Conclusion

A study conducted at Darbhanga Medical College Hospital over one year sheds light on the impact of malaria on children in Darbhanga. The findings reveal a high prevalence of *Plasmodium vivax* and a concentration of cases during the monsoon

season. With a recovery rate of 90%, it is concerning to see a mortality rate of 10%, especially among the most vulnerable groups such as the young. This emphasises the seriousness of malaria and the importance of implementing better preventive measures, early diagnosis, and treatment protocols specifically designed for children. The findings highlight the significance of ongoing public health awareness and the necessity for specific measures to reduce the impact of malaria on children in malaria-prone regions of India.

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